

Towards the understanding of wheel-rail flange squeal: in-situ experiment and genuine 3D profile-enhanced transient modelling

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Abstract

Wheel-rail squeal noise during train turning has been a tricky problem influencing passengers and nearby residents. The tonal curve squeal that mainly occurs at the inner rail has been extensively studied, while the broadband flange squeal that takes place at the outer rail that can be equally annoying is seldom mentioned and hardly investigated. This paper presents a study aiming at understanding the mechanism of wheel-rail flange squeal from phenomenon to the underlying source. The study systematically demonstrates the connection between the observed wheel-rail flange squeal noise and contact force, with measurements taken from a series of well-controlled in-situ experiments on an operating metro line, and numerical simulations. An integrated transient model consisting of three submodels on train dynamics, rail dynamics, and wheel-rail contact incorporating genuine 3D surface irregularities is developed specifically for flange squeal analysis. The developed model can reproduce the characteristics of flange squeal and correlates wheel-rail contact force with the flange squeal noise with satisfactory performance. Features of flange squeal under four-speed levels corresponding to in-situ experiments are reappeared from global dynamics to local contact status. An explanation of the generation mechanism of flange squeal is proposed by measurement observation and confirmed through the proposed model with multiple influencing key factors, including train speed, contact position, shape of contact patch, contact creepages, and wheel and rail irregularities. The present study is expected to establish a footstone for the mechanism comprehension of flange squeal and inspire further research in this area.

Keywords: Wheel-rail flange squeal; Wheel-rail contact; Three-dimensional surface irregularities; Coupled dynamic modelling; Transient modelling; In-situ experiment.

1 Introduction

Wheel-rail squeal noise is caused by imperfect negotiations between train and rail during turning. Squeal noise, including tonal curve squeal noise and broadband flange squeal noise, is categorized as a high-frequency noise source with a large sound pressure level (SPL) and brings great annoyances due to the human's hearing sensitivity to the high frequency noise component. Both kinds of squeal noise have been reported as random, occasional, or even 'erratic' [1–3] because their occurrences can be influenced by environmental conditions (such as weather conditions) at the very same observation locations, and the squeal can also be observed under very low train speed situation. Therefore, although there are a set of mature strategies for rolling noise control, wheel-rail squeal noise mitigation is still an unsolved issue.

The tonal curve squeal is generated largely due to the unsteady lateral creep forces in tight curves and is featured as tonal, high-pitched noise. As early as the 1970s, Rudd [4] presented a theoretical model describing the frictional stick-slip mechanism as a system negative damping (falling friction mechanism). This falling

friction mechanism serves as one of the primary theories for illustrating the generation of curve squeal and has been widely refined and extended. In the transient domain, simulation of curve squeal by multiple elaborated submodels was adopted [5]. This strategy is comprehensive and can incorporate the multibody dynamics of vehicle bodies and the vibrations of both wheels and rails. However, the computational cost is relatively demanding, which inevitably leads to model simplifications when facing a large number of influential factors. A simplified model with reduced DOFs or equivalent analytical models was developed [6] for investigating the mechanism of curve squeal. The simplified model is efficient in illustratively understanding the squeal mechanism and discussing the related influential factors, but it was limited within mechanism analysis and was hard to be applied in engineering practices as an optimization tool. On the other hand, frequency domain simulation with elaborated submodels combined with stability analysis [7] was applied for determining the structural modes that are prone to squeal. Although the proposed frequency domain models have been proven to be efficient in design and optimization [8], the complex eigenvalue analysis or some other dynamic stability analyses can only indicate the squeal-prone modes by an unstable indicator, and it is hard to confirm under which one or several modes the squeal is taking place.

Apart from the falling friction mechanism, the mode-coupling mechanism serves as an alternative and complementary explanation of curve squeal noise. Mode-coupling mechanism provides explanations for ways of energy transfer between two different modes that are theoretically orthogonal to each other, and the instability arises from non-conservative displacement-dependent friction forces even without the negative friction slope [9]. A straightforward explanation was presented by Hoffmann [9] with a 2-DOF model, and stability analysis for curve squeal based on the mode-coupling mechanism without the falling friction feature was discussed [10]. This theory has also been widely used to explain the brake squealing phenomenon with an application of the complex eigenvalue analysis for brake optimization [11,12].

For wheel-rail squeal analysis nowadays, the falling friction mechanism and mode-coupling mechanism have been thought of as coexisting mechanisms in the occurrence of wheel-rail squeal noise, and many researchers have adopted these two mechanisms simultaneously. An assessment of the two mechanisms was proposed by Ding et al. [13], in which the presence of mode-coupling could induce instability with constant friction, and the additional inclusion of negative friction slope that modifies the system damping would transfer the mode-coupling controlled instability to the falling friction controlled one. Investigations of curve squeal under constant friction conditions were presented in both time domain [14] and frequency domain [15]. It is also interesting to find that squeal still exists with a positive friction-velocity curve [16]. Consequently, the generation mechanism of curve squeal has been concluded as structure instability, which was generated from falling friction (negative damping) and friction-induced mode-coupling. Various model development strategies are adaptive to specific concerned aspects, and researchers should dynamically choose the analysis model.

The curve squeal that occurs at the inner rail has been extensively and systematically studied. Similar tonal squeal noise, such as the brake squeal noise [17–22], is also largely attributed to the above two mechanisms. On the contrary, the flange squeal that takes place at the outer rail is seldom investigated, yet it is also a non-negligible annoyance in the railway industry [23]. The flange squeal is generated by wheel-rail flange rubbing (flange contact) at the outer wheel and rail and is an intermittent noise with broadband and even higher frequency component (above 5 kHz). The few papers that mentioned flange squeal were largely based on in-situ monitoring and experimental observations [24–26]. Previous studies incorporating wheel-rail flange contact in this sector were also mainly discussing its relationship with the curve squeal, not the flange squeal. For example, Rudd and Koch [23,27] stated that the flange contact could reduce the curve squeal noise by limiting the large lateral movement of the inner wheel. Fourie [28] discussed the relation between inner rail lateral creep force and the flange contact. It was found that the flange contact could enlarge the force of the

inner leading wheel but reduce the force for the inner trailing wheel. A special investigation was proposed by Squicciarini [29], suggesting that the tonal squeal instability could be generated from the outer wheel-rail pair when considering the presence of two-point contact on grooved rail. This phenomenon was further confirmed by Jiang [30] in field observations, where tonal squeal noise was detected at the outer rail. Nevertheless, the broadband flange squeal has not been investigated until recent years. Kim et. al. [31] conducted both full-scale roller tests and field experiments to investigate both types of squeal noise. It was found that the broadband flange squeal noise possesses a higher frequency component, ranging from approximately 5000 to 9000 Hz (radial natural frequency of wheel, roller test). They suspected that flange squeal could also be generated from the rail with an increased flange contact force since much larger lateral accelerations were measured at the outer rail. Apart from this, most relevant studies merely focused on the engineering aspect for squeal mitigation and lack fundamental investigation on the mechanism. The mitigation measures regarding the flange squeal as a sign of poor lubrication [24], such as the rail thread lubricator, friction modifier (interface layer contributes ‘positive friction’) [25], resilient wheelset, etc., have been proven to be efficient in some cases [16,26,32], but these methods are not generalizable and could not be directly extended as effective and adaptive squealing control strategies. Some other newly developed noise-damping strategies have never been extended to control the flange squeal noise either [33,34]. To the best of the authors’ knowledge, combined experimental and numerical investigations dedicated to comprehending the mechanism of wheel-rail flange squeal have never been conducted previously, despite of the equal annoyance that flange squeal can cause as curve squeal does. An analytical or numerical model is desired to investigate the generation mechanism of flange squeal and to identify relevant dominant factors for more targeted squeal noise mitigation as well as more instructive studies in this area.

This paper provides an insight to understand the generation mechanism of broadband flange squeal, by revealing the linkage between the squeal phenomenon and its underlying source as well as the numerical reappearance of flange squeal characteristics. It should be noted that due to the complexity and redundancy of the noise simulation process [59–62] during a source-orientated mechanism analysis, we chose to reappear the characteristics of flange squeal in the form of contact force. Similar philosophy can also be seen in many curve squeal investigations [1,16,35–39]. A series of well-controlled experiments on an operating metro train under four-speed levels were conducted. Critical information regarding the flange squeal, including the designed dynamic parameters of the metro train and track, wheel and rail three-dimensional surface irregularities, rail dynamic mobility as well as the train-induced rail accelerations and rail-side squeal noise were collected correspondingly. Considering the broadband and intermittent feature of flange squeal, a frequency domain model cannot capture relevant transient characteristics and is thus not appropriate. Therefore, a transient model integrating three submodels (multibody train dynamics, rail dynamics, and exact Kalker’s 3D rolling contact theory [40]) is proposed for flange squeal analysis. The proposed model incorporates genuine 3D scanning measurements of wheel and rail surface irregularities and is capable of reappearing the flange squeal characteristics while preserving both global system dynamics and local wheel-rail contact status. The model is validated through measurements with satisfactory agreements and reveals connections between the flange squeal phenomenon (noise) with the squeal source (contact force). Characteristics of the flange squeal cases and non-flange squeal cases that were distinctively identified in experiments were reappeared through the proposed model in terms of wheel-rail contact force. Finally, the generation mechanism of flange squeal is studied with a global-to-local analysis and a detailed discussion on critical influential factors.

The rest of this paper is organized as follows: Section 2 illustrates the in-situ flange squeal experiments and presents the identified flange squeal results. The flange squeal noise phenomenon is correlated with the measured rail acceleration (denoted as flange squeal vibration). Section 3 elaborates the development of the

integrated transient model for flange squeal analysis. Section 4 demonstrates a detailed validation for the proposed model, which further interconnects flange squeal vibration with contact force. Section 5 presents the characteristic reappearance of wheel-rail flange squeal with the validated model. Global-to-local analysis and additional parameter case studies are included to propose an explanation for the wheel-rail flange squeal generation mechanism.

2 In-situ experiment and phenomenon observation

2.1 Experiment setup

Figure 1 and Figure 2 present the in-situ experiment setup for the identification of wheel-rail flange squeal. The rail accelerations, rail-side noise, wheel and rail surfaces irregularities, track mobility were correspondingly collected at the 1000 m radius of curvature operation line. The occurrence of flange squeal was identified through a combined analysis of rail accelerometers and the rail-side microphones with a 50 kHz sampling frequency. The flange squeal identification includes three steps. First of all, flange squeal vibration was identified by the accelerometers implemented on the outer rail; Secondly, the occurrence of flange squeal noise was further confirmed with the rail-side microphones; Thirdly, a low-pass filter is applied to the rail vibration data for determining the wheelset passing instants and which wheels were squealing. To better control the influential factors, only one train was operated in the midnight maintenance period, and the operating speeds were controlled as 40 km/h, 60 km/h, 80 km/h, 110km/h with repetitive runs to ensure the data reliability. A short-time Fourier transform was conducted to generate the acceleration level and sound pressure level with a 0.1 s window length and 0.05 s signal overlapping for the measurements. The frequency range of interest is 0 ~ 20 kHz.

Figure 1 In-situ experiment of a metro line with 1000 m radius of curvature

Figure 2 Experiment setup

2.2 Flange squeal identification results

Figure 3 shows the filtered rail accelerations under the excitation of passing trains. It effectively identifies the total 16 wheelset passing moments by the signal extreme values. The filter frequency range is determined by the wheelbase (2.5 m) and the maximum operating speed (30.5 m/s).

Flange squeal cases were confirmed at speeds of 110 km/h and 80 km/h through the slender spectrum light band ranging from 5 kHz to 20 kHz. The transient rail accelerations representing flange squeal reach 4000 m/s^2 (Figure 4 (a)(b)) with corresponding intermittent broadband spectrums of both acceleration levels and sound pressure levels (Figure 5 (a)(b)) detected. The flange squeal begins after 4 s, which indicates that it is the traction wheelsets rather than the driven wheelsets that account more for the flange squeal. By contrast, the flange squeal disappears at the speed of 60 km/h and 40 km/h. The transient rail accelerations reduce significantly, with peaks below 350 m/s^2 in the vertical direction and 150 m/s^2 in the lateral one (Figure 4 (c)(d)). Broadband spectrums for both vibration and noise also deteriorate (Figure 5 (c)(d)), indicating the disappearance of flange squeal.

Comparing the spectrum results of rail acceleration level and rail-side sound pressure level, it should be noted that even though the flange squeal noise is not dominant compared with the overall sound pressure level in the current case with a large radius of curvature (1000 m), the broadband and intermittent characteristics are still obvious, especially for the rail accelerations. Therefore, the flange squeal phenomenon can be effectively reflected through acceleration measurements (noted as flange squeal vibration) which are intensive and cannot be ignored, and this is also a reason why we develop a coupled transient model to further analyse the underneath mechanism from the contact perspective.

Figure 3 20 Hz low-pass filtering for wheelset positionings (a) 110 km/h (b) 80 km/h (c) 60km/h (d) 40 km/h

Figure 4 Measured acceleration of outer rail for vertical (first row) and lateral (second row) direction (a) 110 km/h (b) 80 km/h (c) 60 km/h (d) 40 km/h

Figure 5 Flange squeal identification from spectrograms of lateral rail acceleration level (first row) and A-weighted sound pressure level (second row) (a) 110 km/h (b) 80 km/h (c) 60 km/h (d) 40 km/h

3 Model development

In this section, critical steps for the development of a transient simulation model for flange squeal investigation are elaborated. The model consists of three submodels: multibody train dynamics submodel, Timoshenko beam curved rail submodel, and the exact Kalker's 3D rolling contact submodel which serves as the coupling component for the former two submodels. This model captures both global multibody dynamic behaviours up to tens of meters scale and local wheel-rail contact status down to half-millimetre level with decent computational efficiency. This modeling strategy partially remedies the deficiencies of the pure multibody dynamic model in dealing with high-frequency contact problems [41–44] and the finite element model in dealing with coupled vehicle dynamic perspective [3,45]. The goal is to reappear the characteristics of flange squeal through the contact force considering the realistic coupling feature for an operating train. The wheelset modal dynamics and high frequency rail modal dynamics are critical factors for tonal curve squeal, but they are deemed having no contributions to the intermittent and broadband features of flange squeal. To well reproduce the flange squeal events identified in the in-situ experiments, we attempted to recreate the real scenario by using genuine data as far as possible, including parameters from the metro train design material in the test, parameters from the test curved rail along with the dynamic mobility results, as well as detailed 3D wheel and rail surface information.

3.1 Train dynamics submodel

A 31 degree-of-freedoms of a one-coach train dynamic system is developed in this section to simulate the dynamic response of the traction coach during curving. The equation of motion of the train is calculated based on the principle of a stationary value of total potential energy of the train dynamic system proposed by Zeng Qingyuan [46], which is based on the theory that total potential energy for the train in an equilibrium state is stationary. Instead of considering the kinetic energy and potential energy separately (such as the Lagrange equation or the Hamilton principle), this strategy takes all forces during vibration, including the inertia effects, as part of the total conservative potential energy. The detailed train body dimensions and dynamic parameters are listed in Appendix A-1, with more specified system formulation steps for the 31 DOFs train model.

Different from regular train models dedicated to a straight railway line, the relative displacement at the two ends of suspension springs and dampers that are crucial for calculating the potential energy of the dynamic system, is hard to be calculated under one uniform coordinate system for curved cases. Therefore, in our model, the equilibrium state for the train components is set aligned with the track coordinate (Figure 6) to ensure the capability of treating train dynamics in both straight and curved railway lines. When dealing with a curved railway line, the compression and extension of springs and dampers among different components are transferred to the attached bogie coordinate systems for convenience and consistency. The transformation matrix for the three-dimensional case is based on the direction cosine between the new coordinate vectors and the old ones, note that

$$\{u'\} = \begin{bmatrix} x' \\ y' \\ z' \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} e_x' \cdot e_x & e_x' \cdot e_y & e_x' \cdot e_z \\ e_y' \cdot e_x & e_y' \cdot e_y & e_y' \cdot e_z \\ e_z' \cdot e_x & e_z' \cdot e_y & e_z' \cdot e_z \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} x \\ y \\ z \end{bmatrix} = [t]\{u\} \quad (1)$$

where e is a unit vector for the pre-transformed coordinate axis in a fixed global coordinate system, and the e' is the target one; u and u' represent the coordinates in the fixed global and target local frames, respectively.

Figure 6 Coordinate transformation in the curved rails

3.2 Timoshenko beam curved rail submodel

The Timoshenko beam theory is adopted here to build a curved double-rail model, which is designed for taking into account the dynamic characteristics of the train-track system for flange squeal analysis. This paper intends to investigate the flange squeal mechanism, and therefore some potentially peripheral factors such as track plate, bridge, and sleeper systems are not considered here.

For the proposed three-dimensional curved-rail model, each of the Timoshenko beam elements has 12 DOFs, the system matrix is generated by the well-known Hamilton's principle and Hermite shape function. The equation of motion of the curved rail system is given by

$$[M_r]\{\ddot{X}_r\} + [C_r]\{\dot{X}_r\} + [K_r]\{X_r\} = \{F_r\} \quad (2)$$

Where $[M]$, $[C]$ and $[K]$ are global mass, global damping, global stiffness matrices, respectively, and $\{X\}$, $\{F_r\}$ are the displacement and external force vectors in the global coordinate system, respectively. It should be noted that the curved rail system with cant angle and curvature will require a coordinate transformation first before a direct global system assembles [47].

For a Timoshenko beam element, the local element matrix can be generated as

$$\{X_{re}\} = \{u_1 \ v_1 \ w_1 \ r_{x1} \ r_{y1} \ r_{z1} \ u_2 \ v_2 \ w_2 \ r_{x2} \ r_{y2} \ r_{z2}\}^T \quad (3)$$

$$[M_{re}]\{\ddot{X}_{re}\} + [C_r]\{\dot{X}_{re}\} + [K_r]\{X_{re}\} = \{F_{re}\} \quad (4)$$

with

$$[M_{re}] = \int_0^l [N]^T [M_{rr}] [N] dx \quad [K_{re}] = \int_0^l [B]^T [K_{rr}] [B] dx \quad \{F_{re}\} = [N]^T \{F_{rr}\} \quad (5)$$

To conduct coordinate transformation, the transformation matrix is generated from the unit vectors of the local coordinate axis e_i and the global coordinate axis e'_i , note that

$$\{u\} = \begin{bmatrix} x \\ y \\ z \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} e_x \cdot e'_x & e_x \cdot e'_y & e_x \cdot e'_z \\ e_y \cdot e'_x & e_y \cdot e'_y & e_y \cdot e'_z \\ e_z \cdot e'_x & e_z \cdot e'_y & e_z \cdot e'_z \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} x' \\ y' \\ z' \end{bmatrix} = [t_{g2l}]\{u'\}; \quad [T_r] = \begin{bmatrix} t_{g2l} & & & \\ & t_{g2l} & & \\ & & t_{g2l} & \\ & & & t_{g2l} \end{bmatrix} \quad (6)$$

Thus the local dynamic matrix in equation (4) could be transferred for further global matrix assembly.

$$[M_{reg}] = [M_{re}][T_r] \quad [K_{reg}] = [K_{re}][T_r] \quad [F_{reg}] = [T_r]^{-1}[F_{re}] \quad (7)$$

After the system assembly, the fastener springs and dampers are added to the specific DOFs, the coordinate transformations are conducted again to transfer the local spring stiffness and damping parameters into the global dynamic matrices. Manipulation of the Hermite shape function adopted in the Timoshenko beam curved rail model is elaborated in detail in Appendix B.

Figure 7 Curved double-rail FE model (end view)

3.3 Wheel-rail contact model

With the calculated wheel and rail responses, as well as the wheel and rail surface information at the contact point, the potential contact area is generated between the undeformed bodies with spatial distance $d_{ue} < 0$ (calculated from the displacement of wheel and rail with scanned wheel-rail surfaces, which will be further elaborated in this section) through Kalker's variational approach. Main procedures of contact simulation using Kalker's theory regarding virtual work principle for rolling contact are briefly introduced as follows:

The initial contact problem is solved by dividing the potential contact area into N rectangular elements, the element surface pressure and element displacements holds a relation as [48,49]

$$u_i(x_I) = \sum_{j \in \{n,x,y\}} \sum_{J=1}^N A_{iIj}(x_I, x_J) p_j(x_J), \text{ for } I \in \{1 \cdots N\} \text{ and } i \in \{n,x,y\} \quad (8)$$

where the vector $u(x_I)$ represents the I -th element displacement under the element contact pressure within the whole potential contact area, and the vector p represents the element contact pressure, with an assumption of even distribution within one element. The theoretical influence function $A(x_I, x_J)$ presented by Boussinesq and Cerruti [50] is based on the half-space assumption. It effectively connects the body approaching displacement and contact pressure by determining the influence of pressure within element J on the displacement of element I . The vector $\{n,x,y\}$ stands for the normal direction and two tangential ones. Given the pressure of the elements, the overall normal and tangential contact force can be obtained by summing contributions from elements within the meshed potential contact area [51]

$$F_i = \sum_{I=1}^N p_{eI} A_{eI}, \text{ for } i \in \{n,x,y\} \quad (9)$$

where A_{eI} is the area of the I -th element. To keep a contact problem rationally, the following conditions need to be satisfied.

For normal problem:

$$\text{Outside potential contact area: } d_{el} > 0, \quad p_{nl} = 0 \quad (10)$$

$$\text{within the potential contact area: } d_{el} = 0, \quad p_{nl} \geq 0 \quad (11)$$

For tangential problem:

$$\text{outside potential contact area: } p_{tl} = 0 \quad (12)$$

$$\text{in adhesion: } \|s_{tl}\| = 0, \quad p_{tl} \leq g \quad (13)$$

$$\text{in slip: } \|s_{tl}\| > 0, \quad p_{tl} = -g s_{tl} / \|s_{tl}\| \quad (14)$$

$$\text{Coulomb friction: } g(x,t) = \mu p_n(x,t) \quad (15)$$

where the d_{el} stands for the element deformed distance, which indicates that for a regular elastic contact

problem, the two contacting elastic bodies will not interpenetrate with each other in the deformed state, and in turn is combined with the predefined undeformed distance function to output the normal element deformation.

$$d_{el} = d_{ue} + u_n(x_I) \quad (16)$$

the normal and tangential element pressure p_{nl} , p_{tl} outside the potential contact area, is assumed to be zero, and the normal one is also assumed to be non-negative for elements inside. The tangential element pressure inside, on the other hand, is determined by the elements' relative slip velocity [52]

$$s_t = w_t + \dot{u}_t(x_I)/V \quad (17)$$

where w_t represents the rigid slip between two contact bodies. For the wheel-rail rolling problem, it can be calculated through the ratio of rolling velocity and the translational ones in the tangential directions of generated contact coordinate system. Additionally, the elastic contact-induced element velocity $u_t(x_I)$ is also considered by differentiating the element displacement and divided by rolling speed. The adhesion and slip regions are determined by the friction law (Coulomb friction law can be replaced by a velocity-dependent friction coefficient for falling friction mechanism discussion), where the element changes from adhesion to slip once the calculated tangential element pressure reaches the traction bound $g(x,t)$. The above contact model from equations (9) to (17) can be solved with a given contact force or given body displacements by an iterative active-set strategy [40,53].

3.4 Submodels coupling

The one-coach train model (submodel 1) and the double-rail Timoshenko beam curved rail model (submodel 2) are coupled by the wheel-rail contact force (submodel 3) through defining the displacement and velocity for the wheelset and rail at the contact point in the track coordinate system. For consistency, the wheelset coordinate at the contact cross-section is paralleled to the track coordinate system, and the initial spatial coordinates of the inputted wheel profile and rail profile in the contact submodel are determined by the wheel flange back distance, rail gauge distance as well as the rail cant (Figure 8). It needs to be addressed that the contact submodel is dedicated to elastic rolling contact analysis, and the crucial step is to describe the relative responses between two elastic contact bodies. Therefore, the input responses of the wheelsets can be generated by solving the equation of submodel 1 (multibody train model), which could be expressed as:

$$U_{wc} = \begin{bmatrix} \dot{x}_{w1} & y_{w1} & \dot{y}_{w1} & z_{w1} & \dot{z}_{w1} & R_{xw1} & \dot{R}_{xw1} & R_{zw1} & \dot{R}_{zw1} \\ \dot{x}_{w2} & y_{w2} & \dot{y}_{w2} & z_{w2} & \dot{z}_{w2} & R_{xw2} & \dot{R}_{xw2} & R_{zw2} & \dot{R}_{zw2} \\ \dot{x}_{w3} & y_{w3} & \dot{y}_{w3} & z_{w3} & \dot{z}_{w3} & R_{xw3} & \dot{R}_{xw3} & R_{zw3} & \dot{R}_{zw3} \\ \dot{x}_{w4} & y_{w4} & \dot{y}_{w4} & z_{w4} & \dot{z}_{w4} & R_{xw4} & \dot{R}_{xw4} & R_{zw4} & \dot{R}_{zw4} \end{bmatrix} \quad (18)$$

The rolling velocities of wheelsets are set as constant according to the nominal wheel radius to keep a theoretical zero longitudinal creepage (train turning with a constant speed). Rail response, on the other hand, cannot be directly obtained from the solution of equation (2) (submodel 2: double-rail model). A coordinate transformation is conducted first by equation (6) to transfer the rail response from the global coordinate to the target track coordinate, and the Hermite shape functions (Appendix B) are utilized to interpolate the rail responses when the contact points are not on the element nodes. The input responses of the double-rail for both right and left rails in the contact submodel can be expressed as:

$$U_{rc} = \begin{bmatrix} y_{rrw1} & \dot{y}_{rrw1} & z_{rrw1} & \dot{z}_{rrw1} \\ y_{rrw2} & \dot{y}_{rrw2} & z_{rrw2} & \dot{z}_{rrw2} \\ y_{rrw3} & \dot{y}_{rrw3} & z_{rrw3} & \dot{z}_{rrw3} \\ y_{rrw4} & \dot{y}_{rrw4} & z_{rrw4} & \dot{z}_{rrw4} \\ y_{lrw1} & \dot{y}_{lrw1} & z_{lrw1} & \dot{z}_{lrw1} \\ y_{lrw2} & \dot{y}_{lrw2} & z_{lrw2} & \dot{z}_{lrw2} \\ y_{lrw3} & \dot{y}_{lrw3} & z_{lrw3} & \dot{z}_{lrw3} \\ y_{lrw4} & \dot{y}_{lrw4} & z_{lrw4} & \dot{z}_{lrw4} \end{bmatrix} \quad (19)$$

where according to the transformation matrix presented in equation (6), one can obtain the rail contact responses as

$$\begin{bmatrix} y_{rwi} & z_{rwi} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} t_{g2l} & 0 \\ 0 & t_{g2l} \end{bmatrix} \{X_{contact_node}\}_{6 \times 1} \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (20)$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} \dot{y}_{rwi} & \dot{z}_{rwi} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} t_{g2l} & 0 \\ 0 & t_{g2l} \end{bmatrix} \{\dot{X}_{contact_node}\}_{6 \times 1} \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (21)$$

For contact points other than the FE nodes, the rail response can be interpolated through the Hermite shape function (Appendix B), expressed as

$$\begin{bmatrix} y_{rwi} & z_{rwi} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} t_{g2l} & 0 \\ & t_{g2l} \\ & t_{g2l} \\ 0 & t_{g2l} \end{bmatrix} \{X_{contact_element}\}_{12 \times 1} \begin{bmatrix} 0 & N_{v1} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & N_{v2} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & N_{w1} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & N_{w2} & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (22)$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} \dot{y}_{rwi} & \dot{z}_{rwi} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} t_{g2l} & 0 \\ & t_{g2l} \\ & t_{g2l} \\ 0 & t_{g2l} \end{bmatrix} \{\dot{X}_{contact_element}\}_{12 \times 1} \begin{bmatrix} 0 & N_{v1} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & N_{v2} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & N_{w1} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & N_{w2} & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (23)$$

Figure 8 Contact approaching geometry and coordinate systems for wheelset and rail

3.5 Model integration

Up to this step, having all submodels concerning multibody dynamics, rail dynamic response, and wheel-rail contacts developed in Section 3.1-3.3 respectively, and the coupling steps presented in Section 3.4, we can proceed to model integration.

To begin with, the initial displacements of curved rail, wheel-rail contact pairs, and the train vehicle are generated statically. The gravity-induced rail permanent deformation is ignored by setting the initial equilibrium displacement of rail as zero. The contact approaching displacement is calculated by statically loading the gravity of the train on the rails. The train response is calculated by fixing the wheelsets first to calculate the spring compression distance and then adding the displacement of both curved-rail and contact approaching distance. It should be addressed that a static compatibility iteration is also conducted during the initialization process by calculating the three submodels multiple times to finalize the initial condition that satisfies a good force equilibrium for all of the three submodels.

Dynamic iteration begins after decent system initialization. The time step which in general, is set as $dt=1 \times 10^{-5}$ after balancing the convergence rate, computational cost, and accuracy. To solve the dynamic responses, the modal superposition methods based on theoretical impulse response function for curved-rail and the bathe integration method that is demonstrated to be more stable than a regular Newmark one [54] for multibody train model, are adopted.

The vehicle system, which is generated from the ‘set-in-right-position’ law based on the discipline of stationary total potential energy, needs to be reformulated when any one of the wheelsets operates on a new rail element. This is because the orientation of the track coordinate system keeps changing along the curved line. The vehicle response, for consistency, is also altered accordingly through the transformation function in equation (6), which serves as an initial condition for the next timestep.

Finally, the contact forces at one normal and two tangential directions, rail velocity, and displacement responses, and vehicle velocity and displacement responses are outputted as results of the simulation. The detailed simulation process is further demonstrated in Figure 9. To realize the reappearance of flange squeal characteristics, genuine 3D wheel and rail profiles with surface irregularities are essential. Details of the irregularity measurements and the construction of 3D profiles will be elaborated in Section 4.2.

Figure 9 Integration and simulation procedures of the proposed transient model

4 Model validation

This section conducts systematic validation for the proposed model from individual submodels to the integrated one. The flange squeal vibration is correlated with the contact force after the whole model is validated. First of all, indirect validation of the 31 DOFs multibody dynamic model (submodel 1) was conducted through a Taiwan train model proposed in [55] to demonstrate the reliability of the modelling

development procedure. The modal frequency of the first 15 orders is adopted for comparison. A good consistency is achieved. Modal frequencies of the test train are also listed. Detailed results can be found in Appendix A-2. More specific validations of the curved double-rail model by an in-situ impact hammer test, wheel-rail contact justification through 3D scanning measurements, and the final coupled dynamic validation through measured rail accelerations are elaborated in the following sections.

4.1 Mobility validation of the curved-rail model

An on-site impact hammer test was conducted to validate the dynamic properties of the curved rail model. The element size is determined by a combined consideration of trial-and-test strategy and the criterion of one-sixth of the concerned vibration wavelength (pin-pined modal frequency) [56]. The element sizes of 0.05 m, 0.1 m, and 0.3 m with 90 meters of double curved-rails models are developed (Figure 10 (a)). It is shown that the frequency mobility ranging from 10 Hz to 2000 Hz is hardly influenced when the element size is or below 0.1 m. In real circumstances, the rail is so long that most of the bending waves are not travelling back to the excitation point, while it is also impossible to establish a model with infinite length in numerical simulation. To find an optimized model length, the proposed curved-rail model is then established with a length of 30 m, 60 m, 90 m, and 120 m, where the simulated results show that a rail length above 90 m keeps consistent frequency mobility (Figure 10 (b)). Therefore, the proposed curved-rail model is developed with a length of 90 m and an element size of 0.1 m. Comparing the measurement and numerical results (Figure 10 (c)(d)), the calculated results of the proposed curved-rail model also fit reasonably well with the measurements in terms of vertical performance. For the lateral direction, the proposed model also delivers reasonable results in terms of the overall spectrum as well as the pin-pin resonant peaks for both the first-order and the second-order, although a discrepancy is observed for the lateral mobility at the 1340 Hz resonance peak. The discrepancy could be attributed to the web bending mode [57], where the Timoshenko beam element as an integrated bending-shear structure will inevitably neglect some higher-frequency local deformations. Despite this, the proposed model has shown a satisfactory performance for reflecting the coupled behaviours for flange squeal analysis, especially for the lower frequency parts that determine the existence of flange contact.

Table 1 Main parameters of the double-rail model

Notation	Parameter	Motor	Unit
E	Elastic modulus of the steel	2.1×10^{11}	N/m ²
ρ	Density of the rail	7850	kg/m ³
μ	Possion`s effect of steel	0.3	/
J_x	Torsional inertia of rail	3.741×10^{-5}	m ⁴
I_y	Rail second moment of area about cross-sectional Y-axis	3.218×10^{-5}	m ⁴
I_z	Rail second moment of area about cross-sectional Z-axis	5.24×10^{-6}	m ⁴
GJ	Rail torsional stiffness	1.9587×10^5	N m/rad
K_{rv}	Fastener stiffness in track vertical direction	6×10^7	N/m
K_{rh}	Fastener stiffness in track horizontal direction	1×10^7	N/m
C_{rv}	Fastener damping in track vertical direction	7.5×10^3	N s/m
C_{rh}	Fastener damping in track horizontal direction	5×10^3	N s/m
d_{gauge}	Rail gauge distance	1435	mm
$Cant$	Rail cant, angle between the horizontal plane and the track plane	0.832	rad
$d_{fastener}$	Gap between fastener in the track longitudinal direction	0.6	m
R_{rail}	Curve radius of the simulated double-rail	1000	m

Figure 10 Mobility of the curved rail FE model (a) element size discussion (b) model length discussion (c) vertical mobility validation (d) lateral mobility validation

4.2 Contact status assurance through the scanned wheel and rail profiles

The irregularities of two elastic contact surfaces have a significant influence on the contact forces. When performing a contact simulation, the geometric surfaces are the most fundamental prerequisite. It is inevitable to generate inaccurate contact simulation results with an unrealistic wheel and rail profile (initially designed profiles change along with time because of wear, corrosion, etc.). Furthermore, as reported in [53], single-line 2D rail irregularities obtained from track measurement trolley may generate great differences due to different choices of measurement points at the rail cross-section, while general measurement systems are taken for not only rail but also wheel according to the nominal contact positions [58,59], and this may cause discrepancies for wheel-rail contact simulation in the train turning condition. To overcome this issue, instead of solely using an artificial irregularity with power spectral densities (PSD) or a track corrugation measurement trolley that captures the single-line 2D short-wavelength irregularities, real 3D wheel and rail surface irregularities have been used as input for contact simulation in this study. A 3D laser scanner (HandySCAN BLACK|Elite, AMETEK, Inc.) with featured function of capturing 3D point cloud data, was applied on-site for obtaining the short-wavelength rail and wheel surface irregularities of the test train wheels and rails. The 3D scanner has a nominated scanning accuracy of $25\ \mu\text{m}$ when treating a diameter measurement on traceable sphere artifacts (ISO 17025 [60]). However, its capability of capturing the surface irregularity is not well documented, while Affatato et al. [61] demonstrated that this kind of device could achieve an accuracy of at least $10\ \mu\text{m}$ for scanning a volume of $60\times 50\times 50\ \text{mm}$. Hence, short-wavelength irregularities ranging from $10\ \text{mm}$ to $1000\ \text{mm}$ are adopted in the following simulation according to the guide of a typical corrugation measurement trolley (RMF-1100 [62]).

When using a 3D real profile as input, a challenge arises that since the collected data is manifested as a cluster of point cloud measurements, with the existence of wheel and rail irregularities, it is tricky to find the wheel centre and the datum plane perfectly perpendicular to the rail elongation direction. In recognition of this, we propose a specific data pre-processing method to locate the wheel centre and the rail datum plane as accurately as possible. To avoid diluting the paper, detailed procedures of the method are shown in Appendix C.

The preprocessed point cloud data (Figure 11) is then used to generate the cross-sectional wheel and rail profiles for calculating the potential contact area with an initial coordinate system parallel to the corresponding track coordinate system. 3D wheel and rail surface irregularities are also generated from the scanned point cloud data under a three-dimensional interpolation. To balance the computational cost and accuracy, the interpolation is conducted with a spatial gap of 1 mm after 5 mm of filtering interpolation. The experiment setup, initial point cloud data results, and processed wheel-rail profiles and irregularities are presented in Figure 11. wheel and rail surface features such as the nominal radius contact band on wheel and $\lambda \approx 40$ mm corrugation on rail and have been successfully captured, demonstrating the data reliability.

Figure 11 Point cloud data and generated wheel and rail three-dimensional surface irregularities

Due to the high precision 3D scanner scanned over a limited length of both rail and wheel, the medium- and long-wavelength rail irregularity (1 ~ 100 m wavelength) information, which could influence the contact positions, is missing. To overcome this problem, the PSD spectrum from the China Academy of Railway Sciences (CARS) was adopted here to generate the irregularity history with a wavelength from 1 ~ 100 m with a sampling rate of 0.5 m. Further SPLINE interpolation strategy is adopted before being implemented to the flange squeal simulation system.

Figure 12 Rail irregularity with wavelength 1 ~ 100 m (a) vertical (b) lateral

4.3 Coupled validation of the proposed flange squeal simulation model

Kalker's rolling contact model by variational approach is widely accepted as a detailed and 'exact' contact simulation strategy. The contact simulation solver adopted in this paper has also been validated with the Manchester wheel-rail contact benchmark [63], where the validation process can be found in [52]. The benchmark process will not be presented in this paper for brevity. Given a validated contact stress prediction

solver, the accuracy of the wheel-rail contact simulation results can be ensured through realistic and detailed geometry inputs for the contact surfaces. Therefore, the contact simulation result in our model is further ensured by the corresponding wheel and rail surface point cloud data that captures detailed geometry information which has been presented in section 4.2.

Finally, due to the difficulties in a direct measurement of the high frequency wheel-rail contact force, the simulated rail accelerations from the integrated transient model with the well-validated rail submodel (section 4.2) serve as an intermediate product to validate with the measured rail accelerations. Considering the available frequency range of a Timoshenko beam element, rail vibration results at a nearby measurement location (under corresponding wheel-rail profiles and rail mobility) without the extremely high frequency component are used to ensure the reliability of the simulated wheel-rail contact force.

In the time domain (Figure 13), the simulated rail acceleration at both wheelset passing instants and between wheelset passing periods are at the same magnitude levels as the measured ones. In frequency domain (Figure 14), the simulated spectrums have relatively consistent trends with the measured results, especially, three spectrum peaks around 600 Hz, 1100 Hz, and 1600 Hz are successfully captured by the proposed model. A reasonable consistency is achieved, which specifically confirms the reliability of the proposed transient model in terms of effectively relating the wheel-rail contact force output with the coupled system dynamics and the contact surface irregularities as inputs.

Till the end of this step, the connection between flange squeal vibration and the flange squeal excitation force as the squeal source is fully revealed. The validated model can now be applied to conduct a mechanism comprehension for the wheel-rail flange squeal through a contact perspective. The characteristic reappearance of flange squeal and corresponding parameter case studies are presented subsequently.

Figure 13 Validation of rail accelerations at speed 83 km/h (23.06 m/s) (a) measured vertical acceleration (b) measured lateral acceleration (c) one-second validation of vertical acceleration (d) one-second validation of lateral acceleration

Figure 14 Spectrum validation of rail accelerations at speed 83 km/h (23.06 m/s) (a) vertical (b) lateral

5 Characteristic reappearance and mechanism comprehension for flange squeal

The connections among flange squeal noise, flange squeal vibration and contact force have been established in the previous sections. Considering the broadband and intermittent features of wheel-rail flange squeal noise, a specific type of impulse excitation having the same features is thought to generate the flange squeal. Based on this point of view, a global-to-local analysis and a parameter discussion are presented in this section to elaborate on where does the impulse excitation (flange squeal) come from.

Characteristic reappearance of experimental flange squeal cases and non-flange squeal cases (refer to Section 2) is conducted through the validated model in section 5.1. The global contact forces induced by the coupled dynamic behaviours and the contact stress distribution inside the local contact patch are step-by-step presented and comprehensively discussed. The operation speed is set according to the experiment conditions as 110 km/h (27.7 m/s), 80 km/h (22.2 m/s), 60 km/h (16.7 m/s), 40 km/h (11.1 m/s). Given the flange squeal characteristic reappearance results, special attention is paid to discussing the connections between the flange squeal and wheel and rail irregularities (section 5.2). Four additional cases aiming to make a clearer investigation on how irregularities contribute to the flange squeal are designed. Roles of medium- and long-wavelength irregularities and short-wavelength wheel and rail irregularities are figured out, respectively. Conclusions are drawn to explain the generation mechanism of flange squeal from the contact perspective.

5.1 Characteristic reappearance of the flange squeal

The global-to-local analysis based on the proposed model is presented in Figure 15 to Figure 22 for flange squeal reappearance in correspondence to the in-situ experiment operation conditions. In Figure 15, the train velocity is found to be one of the most important global factors inducing the flange squeal in this large radius of curvature case. The impulse-like lateral contact forces reach 107 kN for 110 km/h at $T=0.459$ s and 97 kN for 80 km/h at $T=0.631$ s. Similar peaks can also be found for the vertical contact forces, while the impulse-like feature is not as distinctive as the lateral ones do. For the lower speed cases (60 km/h and 40 km/h), the impulse-like feature deteriorates drastically, although both vertical and lateral contact force peaks can still be found at $T=0.815$ s with lateral force peak of 39 kN for the 60 km/h case and $T=1.22$ s with lateral force peak of 24 kN for the 40 km/h case.

The broadband intermittent feature is the most fundamental characteristic for the flange squeal and therefore can be used as a primary indicator in the characteristic reappearance. A short-time Fourier transform was conducted for the transient contact forces to identify the occurrence of flange squeal (Figure 16). The spectrograms reflect obvious flange squeal characteristic with broad-band spectrums at $T=0.4 \sim 0.55$ s and $T=1.0 \sim 1.15$ s for 110 km/h and $0.55 \sim 0.75$ s for 80 km/h, especially for contact forces in lateral direction. It is well known that the broadband features are induced by the impulse-like transient contact forces, and this kind of spectrum begins to deteriorate and become incomplete for $T=1.4 \sim 1.6$ s at 80 km/h and cases of speed levels as 60 km/h and 40 km/h. The deterioration of the broadband excitation feature can therefore

preliminarily be attributed to the influence of train operation speed. Since a lower speed level cannot establish a force peak within a very short period (impulse-like contact force), which induces the disappearance of flange squeal.

Figure 15 Transient contact forces of the front outer wheelsets

(a) 110 km/h (b) 80 km/h (c) 60 km/h (d) 40 km/h

Figure 16 Spectrogram of the vertical (first row) and lateral (second row) contact force at front outer wheel

(a) 110 km/h (b) 80 km/h (c) 60 km/h (d) 40 km/h

The train operation speed accompanying the medium- and long-wavelength irregularities influence the wheel-rail contact positions in a curved rail line. Wheel and rail contact positions (Figure 17) and the irregularities at the contact point with corresponding RMS of irregularities are presented (Figure 18) to further analyse the relationship between flange squeal and contact positions as well as contact surface irregularities. Here, the contact position is described in the wheel profile coordinate system and rail profile coordinate system respectively. For the cases with flange squeal (110 km/h and 80 km/h), the impulse-like contact force occurs at the contact positions $y_{wp} = -33$ mm for the wheel profile coordinate and $y_{rp} = -25$ mm for the rail profile coordinate. In comparison, for $T = 1.4 \sim 1.6$ s at 80 km/h, the contact positions are located at $y_{wp} = -29.4$ mm and $y_{rp} = -21.6$ mm. For the cases without flange squeal, the contact positions are $y_{wp} = -30$ mm, $y_{rp} = -22$ mm for 60 km/h and $y_{wp} = -28$ mm, $y_{rp} = -20$ mm for 40 km/h. The disappearance of flange squeal is found to

correspond to the reduction of short-wavelength surface irregularities (to be discussed in the next paragraph) and the disappearance of wheel-rail flange contact, which will be further confirmed in the later local contact patch discussion.

Figure 18 presents both the wheel and the rail irregularities in three wavelength ranges (10-30 mm, 30-100 mm, and 100-1000 mm) for the observed contact positions. For the rail, the wheel-rail flange contact region shows larger irregularities (RMS around 3 ~ 4 μm) compared with the wheel-rail thread contact region (RMS around 2 ~ 3 μm) in the wavelength 10-30 mm. The corrugation region ($y_{rp} = -8$ mm) shows an obvious increase in the irregularity (RMS around 8 μm) at wavelength 30-100 mm, which corresponds to the observed corrugation wavelength $\lambda \approx 40$ mm (Figure 11). A similar feature is found for the wavelength 100-1000 mm (RMS around 15 μm). As for the wheel, the surface irregularity variations are more drastic compared with the rail one, especially for those within wavelength 10-30 mm. For a flange contact region with $y_{wp} = -33$ mm, the RMS of irregularities at wavelength 10-30 mm can increase to 35 μm , while for the region around nominal radius point (or wheel-rail thread contact area), the RMS of irregularities is below 3 μm . For the wavelength 30-100 mm, a similar variation is obtained, with RMS of irregularities around 20 μm for flange contact region, and RMS irregularities below 3 μm for thread contact region. The irregularity variation becomes mild for the wavelength range 100-1000 mm, with RMS of irregularities around 20 μm for flange contact region, and RMS irregularities around 4 μm for thread contact region.

Jointly considering the wheel-rail contact positions and the measured wheel-rail surface irregularities, the impulse-like contact force (flange squeal indicator) is most likely to be caused by the wheel surface irregularities, especially for those within wavelength 10-100 mm. Moreover, a higher speed tends to cause a deeper flange contact, which consequently alters the contact point from a low surface irregularity region to a much higher surface irregularity region and thus causes the impulse-like contact force. The measured high irregularity levels in these regions are considered to be caused by occasional and abnormal contacts (e.g., wheel-rail scratch) during train turning. Further studies on this fundamental wear problem are preferred to confirm this thinking, but it is not within the scope of this research. Here, we continue to investigate the cause of flange squeal by having a more detailed view within the contact patch to figure out how contact formulates during flange squeal.

Figure 17 Contact positions at speed (a) 110 km/h (b) 80 km/h (c) 60 km/h (d) 40 km/h

Figure 18 irregularities and RMS at contact positions for (a) wheel surface and (b) rail surface with wavelength 10-30 mm (1st row), 30-100 mm (2nd row), and 100-1000 mm (3rd row)

Contact patch acts as a box-window filter when treating short wavelength wheel and rail surface irregularities, this behaviour is named as contact filter effect [53]. A closer analysis for the 110 km/h case with flange squeal is presented to reveal the three-dimensional contact status of initializations, developments, occurrences, and terminations process for the flange squeal (Figure 19). It is not strange to find that, instead of an impeccably elliptical contact patch that is generally assumed in Hertz contact theory, the measured wheel-rail profiles lead to an irregular patch even at the initialization instant (Figure 19 (a)). This can be attributed to the wear of both wheel and rail surfaces along with the train operation time. When the train begins turning, the contact patches move to the rail inner gauge side, with patch separation and a shrinking trend of contact patch size (Figure 19 (b)). The wheelset continues to move outward, where the flange contact begin to initialize with increasing lateral contact force and smaller contact area (Figure 19 (c)). During flange squeal, the contact patch tends to keep moving outward causing further slender flange contact, and is finally confined by the drastically increased lateral contact stiffness due to the geometrical shape between wheel flange and rail inner gauge. It is commonly known that great stiffness tends to cause a force peak because of the high sensitivity of displacement and force relationship at the flange contact position. Figure 19 (d)(e) show the contact patch during flange squeal. The wheel-rail flange contact formulates a much slender contact area compared with the regular thread contact position as an elliptic-like patch. This shrinkage of the contact area potentially impairs the contact filter effect, which may serve as an additional reason for causing flange squeal. Finally, Figure 19 (f) shows an enlargement of the wheel-rail contact patch, which then theoretically increases the contact filter effect, meanwhile, the wheel and rail surface irregularities reduce to moderate levels.

Figure 20 shows the internal traction stress distribution of contact patches and corresponding creepages. The creepage is defined to describe the relative movement for the rolling and the translation movement, where the detailed definition could be found in [49]. Due to the assumption of constant velocity for train operation, the wheelset rolling velocity is set to be equal to the translational speed according to the nominal radius of the wheel. Figure 20 (a) and (b) show a stick-slip contact patch indicating moderate overall creepages at the wheel-rail thread contact position, the traction force is kept under the traction bound determined by the Column

friction law. The traction forces begin to saturate along with the occurrence of wheel-rail flange contact (Figure 20 (c)(d)(e)) due to a larger wheel radius and radius difference inside the patch, which induces larger longitudinal and spin creepages, respectively. These increased creepages at the contact position may lead to a more intensified irregularity input from the wheel surface. The overall lateral creepage is kept within $\pm 0.21\%$, which does not show an obvious connection to the flange squeal in our large radius of curvature case. The creepages of contact patches are listed in Table 2.

The above analysis within the contact patches covers the overall process of flange squeal. Contact filter effect and creepages are both identified as additional factors influencing the flange squeal. They interact with the previously identified wheel-rail surface irregularities and are indirectly influenced by the train operation speed that determines the contact positions. Given the complicated mutual effects or reverse effects among various factors, a comprehensive parameter analysis is desired. For example, a global sensitivity analysis, which could incorporate statistical parameters, is an optimum choice to further identify the sensitivity of all factors on flange squeal, this process remains infeasible for the current integrated transient model due to the extreme computational cost when treating dozens of statistical parameters. Therefore, we confine ourselves to the aspect regarding irregularities, which were deemed as the most fundamental reason inducing impulse-like contact force, in the followed investigation. Clarifications on how medium- and long-wavelength rail irregularity and short-wavelength wheel and rail surface irregularities can cause the flange squeal, are to be presented.

Figure 19 The 110 km/h outer wheel contact patch location (a) contact initialization (b) transferring to flange contact (d) initializing flange contact (d) flange squeal 1 (e) flange squeal 2 (f) end flanging

Figure 20 The stick-slip feature of 110 km/h outer wheel contact (red arrows represent the rolling direction) (a) contact initialization (b) transferring to flange (d) initializing flange contact (d) flange squeal 1 (e) flange squeal 2 (f) end flanging

Table 2 Creepages of wheel-rail contact corresponds to Figure 20

Time (s)	Creepage		
	Longitudinal (%)	Lateral (%)	Spin (rad/m)
0.005	0.1302	0.2131	0.0170
0.4	0.3913	-0.2037	0.0357
0.445	1.1763	-0.3306	0.0763
0.46	1.7980	0.2589	0.1406
0.485	1.6902	0.1801	0.1311
0.55	0.7862	0.1330	0.0498

5.2 Influence of wheel-rail irregularities on flange squeal

Four additional cases are designed in this section to investigate the roles of medium- and long-wavelength rail irregularity and short-wavelength wheel and rail surface irregularities on the occurrences and characteristics of flange squeal. The modified cases are based on the original 110 km/h case with detected broadband flange squeal.

Table 3 Rail irregularity cases

No. of CASE	Case description
1	Eliminate the medium- and long-wavelength rail irregularity
2	Eliminate the short-wavelength rail irregularity
3	Eliminate the short-wavelength wheel irregularity
4	Eliminate both wheel and rail short-wavelength irregularities

The transient contact forces with the three additional cases are presented in Figure 21, and the corresponding short-time Fourier transformed results are presented in Figure 22. Impulse-like contact force does not appear in case 1, which ignores the medium- and long-wavelength rail irregularity, indicating that the flange squeal cannot be generated due to the miss of flange contact. Impulse-like contact force and broadband characteristics can be detected in case 2 and case 3. Case 3 shows a larger contact force peak than case 2, and the broadband flange squeal feature can be found in $T=0.4 \sim 0.55$ s and $T=1.0 \sim 1.15$ s, whereas it can only be found in $T=0.45 \sim 0.55$ s in case 2 with a relatively moderate broadband spectrum. Case 4 shows a moderate contact peak force in Figure 21 (d), but the broadband spectrogram is not successfully established and is thus a non-squeal case.

Four comparisons indicate that the wheel and rail short-wavelength irregularities cast a great impact on the formulation of impulse-like contact force with a broadband feature. The medium- and long-wavelength rail irregularity can indeed establish a peak of contact force (case 1), but the force increment rate is too mild to formulate a broadband spectrogram, i.e., the medium- and long-wavelength rail irregularity cannot cause the flange squeal alone. Through comparison among case 2, case 3 and case 4, it is found that the short-wavelength wheel and rail surface irregularities cannot generate the impulse-like contact force and the broadband spectrogram due to the miss of flange contact, or more straightforward to say, the miss of a contact transition from lower surface irregularity region to a higher one. Therefore, medium-and-long rail irregularity in the current large radius of curvature condition is also one prerequisite for flange squeal.

In all, in the current large radius of curvature case, the medium- and long-wavelength irregularity is critical to formulating the wheel-rail flange contact when the operation speed is below 110 km/h. Its practical effect is to cause a transition of the contact point. The higher short-wavelength wheel and rail surface irregularities at the wheel flange and rail inner gauge regions are indispensable for generating an impulse-like contact force with a broadband spectrogram. Missing either medium- and long-wavelength irregularity or short-wavelength surface irregularities cannot induce flange squeal. From a general view of speaking, the flange squeal noise can be attributed to an intense rubbing on contact surfaces with a transition from a lower irregularity region to a higher one.

Figure 21 Transient contact forces of the front outer wheelsets at 110 km/h (30.6 m/s)

(a) case 1 (b) case 2 (c) case 3 (d) case 4

Figure 22 Spectrogram of the vertical (first row) and lateral (second row) contact force of the front outer wheel at 110 km/h (30.6 m/s) (a) case 1 (b) case 2 (c) case 3 (d) case 4

6 Conclusions

This paper presents a research effort attempting to understand the generation mechanism of wheel-rail flange squeal from the measurement phenomenon to the underlying source (contact force), which to the authors' best knowledge, is for the first time conducted on flange squeal.

A series of well-controlled in-situ experiments were carried out on an operating metro line. The intermittent, broadband, and extremely high frequency flange squeal vibration and noise were successfully captured from the in-situ experiments.

A transient model consisting of three submodels was developed and integrated to numerically reappear the characteristic of flange squeal in the form of contact force. The proposed model intakes realistic in-situ experiment parameters, as well as genuine wheel and rail profiles generated from in-situ 3D scanning data of surface irregularities as inputs to best simulate the real scenario. With a combined measurement discussion and comprehensive model validation, the generation of the flange squeal noise phenomenon is step-by-step connected to the flange squeal rail acceleration and finally to the wheel-rail contact force as the phenomenon-to-source analysis.

Flange squeal characteristic reappearance simulation and parameter study regarding irregularities are then conducted under the conditions of the in-situ experiment to give a detailed mechanism comprehension from the global aspect concerning coupled train dynamics to the local wheel-rail contact status. Specific findings are listed as follows:

1. The railway operation speed and medium- and long-wavelength rail irregularity are identified as two of the dominant factors that cause flange contact, which is the prerequisite of flange squeal;
2. Slender contact patch size is detected in the flange contact region, which theoretically induces a greater sensitivity of contact force to the short-wavelength wheel and rail surface irregularities. Therefore, the deterioration of contact filter effect is another reason for flange squeal;
3. Larger surface irregularity levels at the wheel flange and rail inner gauge have been confirmed through the in-situ experiment. They are found to be responsible for the generation of impulse-like contact force and broadband spectrum feature (flange squeal) with the occurrence of flange contact.

As an overall concluding remark, the generation mechanism of wheel-rail flange squeal is attributed to

existence of impulse excitation. The impulse excitation is generated through the wheel-rail flange contact where higher level surface irregularities exist at these contact regions. To be more straightforward, the broadband and intermittent wheel-rail flange squeal can be caused by an intensive rubbing between two contact surfaces with a transition from a lower level short-wavelength irregularity region to a higher level one.

It should be admitted that this research serves as an initial attempt for understanding the generation mechanism of flange squeal. Many more investigations are still needed, such as how do impulse excitation interact with wheel and rail high frequency modes? and which contact point is more likely to excite modes that are likely to radiate noise efficiently? Complementary explanations or alternative theories may be found after incorporation of more and more relevant dynamic systems. Further investigations that can achieve flange squeal prediction are also being conducted (considering additional dynamic systems, such as wheel and rail modal dynamics, difference radius of curvature, noise radiation part, etc.). A comprehensive sensitivity index of more relevant influential factors for the wheel-rail flange squeal is expected in the future.

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